

Research Article

Assessment of the Tourism Potentials of Two Waterfalls in South-West Nigeria

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Abstract

Tourism could be an antidote for the present economic recession in Nigeria if well harnessed. The present study assessed the abounding potentials for tourism in Olumirin waterfall, Erin Ijesa and Arinta waterfall, Ipole-Iloro Ekiti over a period of six months from September 2015 to February 2016. The study assessed: the tourist attractions, the various hospitality facilities of the two sites for ecotourism purposes and their income generating potentials. The methods used for data collection were; direct observations and oral interview of the visitors to the waterfalls. The result of the study revealed that, hospitality facilities present at both sites were; relaxation centers, reliable security, a guest house around Olumirin waterfall, a souvenir shop where drinks and toiletries can be bought, an uncompleted restaurant, good assessable road that leads to Arinta Waterfall. It is evident from the study that the levels of development in the two sites were very low but still generating some income for the states. There is also the potential to progress as the years progresses if given attention. The study concluded that if tourist sites of this nature are well maintained, it would bring addition revenue to the state in which they are domicile (Osun and Ekiti) and improve their Internally Generated Revenue (IGR). The study therefore recommended that state governments should give attention to these tourist sites so as to upgrade it to a world class tourist centre which will attract people all over the world.

Keywords: Tourism potentials, Erin-Ijesa waterfall, Olumirin waterfall, Arinta waterfall, Osun and Ekiti States. South-West, Nigeria.

Received: 20 January 2017

Accepted: 23 March 2017

Introduction

Nigeria is endowed with beautiful scenes and interesting places that are worthy for the eyes to behold. (Nigerian Bulletin, 2014). Nigeria is a country situated in the western coastal region of the African continent. The country is rich in natural beauty like, long blue beaches, rivers and lakes, forests, breathtaking views of the waterfalls and soothing environment (Compare Infobase, 2017). The natural beauty is a main factor behind the up-gradation of Nigeria tourism. Tourism in Nigeria is growing rapidly and it is among the tourism industry is a good revenue earner for the country. Nigeria has a wide range of tourist activities to offer. It is a coastal country and the main attraction for the tourists is the long beaches and the marine activities. Apart from this, the other attractions are the historical monuments, exciting trips to the tropical forests, exploring the wildlife, art and culture and the lifestyle of the country. Traditions and culture of the country represents the simplicity in the lifestyle of the dwellers. The markets of Nigeria showcase the handicrafts and sculptures, the hotels and other accommodation facilities represent the warm hospitality and local customs and the calm and peaceful environment enhances into the beauty of the country. (Compare Infobase, 2017).

All the geo-political region of Nigeria have abundance tourist sites and the south-west is not left behind. In the south west, we have Olumo rock in Ogun State, the University of Ibadan Zoological centre in Oyo State among others. For the purpose of this study, Osun and Ekiti states are taken as case study. Osun and Ekiti States are blessed with abundant tourism potentials, such as wildlife, Waterfalls Mountains and other rich festival, architecture, and craft, but most of these resources are not properly managed and developed. The facts remain that Olumirin and Arinta waterfalls have high potentials for attracting tourist and increasing the Internally Generated Revenue (IGR) of their states, but their tourism features had not been well developed and packaged. Therefore, these aforementioned challenges are making these tourist sites unattractive and had prompted this research work. The study therefore identified the various tourist attractions and assessed the various hospitality facilities available to tourists in Arinta and Olumirin waterfalls for developing and maximizing the vast resources of the site for ecotourism purposes. The study was carried out at Olumirin waterfall. It is located in Erin-Ijesa, Oriade Local Government Area of Osun State, Nigeria and Arinta Waterfall is located in Ipole-Iloro Ekiti in Ekiti-West Local Government Area, Ekiti State (Figure 1). Erin-Ijesa town is situated within latitude 7°30' and 8°45' North and longitude 4°31' and 5°East. (Odeyemi *et al.*, 2011) while Ipole-Iloro Ekiti is located on latitude 7.31°N and longitudes 5.0°E.

Methodology

The Initial reconnaissance survey was carried out for four weeks at both sites, in September 2015 to locate and assess the potential tourism features of Arinta and Olumirin waterfalls. Subsequent visits were made twice in a month from the month of October 2015 to February 2016. Questions were asked 'face to face' during the oral interview and the villagers were encouraged to respond as honest as possible. Observations involved on-site data collection, and in most cases, it is referred to as un-obstructive method of research, un-obtrusive in such a way that the observer is not in contact with the observed and still carries out observation successfully (Veal, 2006). The purpose of carrying out an observation in this research work is to study the level of tourism development in the two tourist centers. A digital camera (12.1 mega pixels) was used to take photographs of the unique tourism features present in the study areas.

Results

Olumirin and Arinta water cascading from heights of about 60 and 50 meters high respectively (Plate 1 and 2). The cascading which is in seven levels at the two sites is captivating providing natural beautiful scenery to behold by tourists, who preferred to sit around the first fall to enjoy the cool breeze. It was also observed that the waterfall areas are naturally endowed with dense and evergreen vegetation which serve as shades for tourist and the scenery produced by the undulating topography of the waterfall areas. This is in line with Nairaland Forum (2008), documented that tourist attractions in Nigeria can be classified as Natural Attractions: that has abundant physical attractions such as hills, caves, springs, lakes and mountains across the entire country. These fascinating features and alluring scenes are good sites for leisure, adventure and other tourism-related endeavours. Example of these physical attractions are old Oyo National Park, Yankari Games Reserve in Bauchi; Obudu (Protea) Cattle Ranch, in cross River State and the Jos Wildlife Park in Plateau State. It was also observed that most tourists could not reach the seventh fall of Olumirin Waterfall which is at Efon Alaaye in Ekiti state. Plate 3 is a picture of a hut found on the top of the hill. Tourist could only reach the second fall, due to the difficulties involved in the climbing. The animals sighted around the waterfalls are, Prawn (*Caridina Africana*), Mona Monkey (*Cercopithecus mona*), Cattle egret (*Ardeola ibis*), Catfish (*Clarias spp*), Sand Crab (*Ocypoda africana*), Squirrel (*Xerus erythropus*) and Giant Land Snail (*Archachatina maginata*) Sand Crab (*Ocypoda africana*), were sighted at the waterfall areas (Table 1) sighted at Olumirin Waterfall. This also agrees with the documentation of answer.com (2017) that The Singapore Zoo and Night

Safari offer a night-time view of animals in their habitats and the Jurong Bird Park houses exotic birds from around the world. Plate 4 shows a pool where Catfish and Prawn were sighted.

Plate 5 shows a small cave at Arinta Waterfall, it was observed that the animals stay very close to the waterfall. This could be because animals also need water for survival. Table 2 shows the assessment of the hospitality facilities present at the two tourist sites, Olumirin waterfall is less than 1km from the highways; the road leading to the center is rough and dusty while, the road leading to Arinta Waterfall is tarred; the road ascends steeply and confronts the gigantic Efon Alaaye Ridge. This agrees with the findings of Robinson (2013), that accessibility is an important part of every tourist attraction. Without adequate access, an attraction might suffer from under visitation (and potentially a subsequent lack of economic viability) or from crowding issues (for example, due to traffic jams). Plate 6 and 7 shows the relaxation centers and facilities, five at Arinta and eight at Olumirin Waterfall. The only available accommodation at Olumirin Waterfall is a guest house very close to the tourist site, and there is no available accommodation at Arinta Waterfall. Plate 8 is an uncompleted building meant to be a Standard Restaurant at Olumirin waterfall, however there is a souvenir shop where drinks and toiletries can be bought. Plate 9 and 10 shows the Steps and walkways that were constructed by the Osun State Government to facilitate easy access to the first fall and the relaxation centers at Olumirin waterfall.

Discussion

The two waterfalls studied have great potentials for tourism development in the states, if properly harnessed, well packaged and marketed, According to Robinson (2013), almost any place in the world can become an attraction as long as it is well packaged and sold to its niche market; the people for whom the attraction is best suited. Tourists visiting the sites were attracted by the waterfalls and scenarios of the sites. Beautiful natural scenery as well as cultural artifacts for the purpose of tourism is available in the rural communities than in the urban areas. It was noted further that the rural areas create social safety and enabling environment for recreation and tourism. Olumirin and Arinta waterfalls have a good natural environment combined with rich culture and history, this form the basis of what makes the community a tourist destination. The common cultural festivals at the two study areas were; Egungun (Masquerades), New Yam and Ogun (god of iron) festivals. Egungun festival is celebrated in the month of August and April at Erin Ijesa and Ipole-Iloro Ekiti respectively. Ogun festival is celebrated at the beginning of the

chieftaincy installation and New Yam festival is celebrated annually during the harvest of New Yam. These festivals attract both indigenes and non-indigenes. Most of the animals in the tourist sites have been wiped out through hunting. The enormous loss of animals is directly attributed to illegal hunting or poaching which goes on at the sites (Osunsina, 2004). The available hospitality facilities at Olumirin waterfall are relaxation centers and a souvenir shop which were observed to be improperly managed. The infrastructural facilities at the tourist sites are in deplorable state at Olumirin waterfall. This is evident by the uncompleted but abandoned building which was supposed to be a standard restaurant (Plate 8). Relaxation centers at Arinta waterfall (five in number) were newly constructed. These are meant to serve as visitors sitting facilities after exploring the waterfall and the surrounding forest (Plate 6), Also at Olumirin waterfall, there are eight relaxation centers for visitors (Plate 7), and these were provided by the Government of Ekiti State and Oriade Local Government of Osun State. The Government of Ekiti State has been able to improve the road network leading to Arinta waterfalls thereby making accessibility to the sites easier. However, the road leading to Olumirin waterfall is not good even though it attracts more visitors due to its location being along the major highway (Akure-Ilesha expressway). Accessibility to the Olumirin waterfall have been made easier with the construction of walkways to the waterfall sites (Plate 9 and 10). This effort on the path of Oriade Local Government is towards developing and harnessing the potentials of the waterfalls and attracting more visitors to the sites. In contrast, Arinta waterfalls have not been developed for easy accessibility by the visitors; logs of wood are sometimes used to access parts of the sites. There is no available accommodation at Arinta waterfall, the only available accommodation is a guest house very close to Olumirin waterfall. Hospitality facilities are helpful for tourism development in the state, because accommodation for tourists is an important consideration in planning for tourism apart from transportation, whatever structures need to be put up must not be out of place within the local community. Quality comfort should be the guiding principle and luxury. Tourism planning should also take into account the wishes of the local residents. There is a police station at the two sites and tour guards normally accompany visitors when going into the areas, health centers and clinics are equally available at the two study areas. Communication facilities enabled by network provider such as MTN and GLO are available at the sites. This makes communication with the other parts of the country readily available and enabled.

Conclusion

Olumirin and Arinta waterfalls are blessed with great tourism potentials, which consist of cultural and natural attractions. This research confirmed that the tourist centers are at the low level of development. There are little awareness and tourism facilities (i.e. accommodation, restaurants and local transportation) to attract and accommodate tourists. There is need to explore and develop these potentials in order to provide adequate information to the government, for proper management and packaging for effective marketing. This will also change the orientation of the public and invariably improve tourists' visitation to the sites.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following are therefore recommended for policy makers:

- i. The state government of Osun and Ekiti State should give attention to these tourist sites so as to upgrade it to a world class tourist centre which will attract people from all over the world.
- ii. Infrastructural facilities such as good roads and electricity should also be provided at these tourist sites so as to make it accessible to visitors

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ISSN: 2251 - 0486 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

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Figure1: Location of the study sites in southwestern Nigeria.

Source: Field survey, 2016

Table 1: Animals Sighted around Olumirin and Arinta Waterfalls

Animals	Scientific names	Olumirin waterfall	Arinta waterfall
Prawn	<i>Caridina Africana</i>	√	—
Kob	<i>Kobus kobus</i>	√	√
Mona monkey	<i>Cercopithecus mona</i>	—	√
Cattle egret	<i>Ardeola ibis</i>	√	—
Catfish	<i>Clarias spp</i>	√	—
Sand Crab	<i>Ocypoda africana</i>	√	√
Squirrel	<i>Xerus erythropus</i>	√	√
Giant land Snail	<i>Archachatina marginata</i>	√	√

Source: Field Survey, 2016

Table 2: Assessment of the Hospitality Facilities at Olumirin and Arinta Waterfalls

Facilities	Olumirin waterfall	Arinta waterfall
Accessibility(Road)	Bad(Rough and Dusty)	Good(Tarred)
Accommodation	√	—
Souvenir shops	√	—
Games(outdoor)	√	—
Restaurant/Eatery	—	—
Security	√	√

Source: Field survey, 2016 √: Present, —: Absent

Plate 1: Olumirin Waterfall showing the first level falls. Source: Field Survey, 2016

Plate 2: Arinta waterfall showing the first Olumirin Waterfall. Source: Field Survey, 2016

Plate 3: A hut situated at the top of Level Falls. Source: Field Survey, 2016.

Plate 4: Pool where *Caridina Africana* (Prawn) and *Clarias spp* (Cat Fish) were sighted at Olumirin Waterfall. Field Survey, 2016.

Plate 5: A Small Cave at Arinta Waterfall where some animals live.
Source: Field Survey, 2016.

Plate 6: Relaxation Centers at Arinta Waterfall. Source: Field Survey, 2016.

Plate 7: Relaxation Centers at Olumirin Waterfall. Source: Field Survey, 2016.

Plate 8: Abandoned Standard Restaurant at Olumirin Waterfall. Source: Field Survey, 2016.

Plate 9: Steps leading to the relaxation centers at Olumirin waterfall
Source: Field Survey, 2016.

Plate 10: Walk-way at Olumirin Waterfall
Source: Field Survey, 2016.